

Study of interfacial bonding of flax fibre /poly(L-Lactide)

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SUMMARY

Vegetal fibre reinforced biopolymers called biocomposites are an alternative to the glass fibre reinforced thermoset composites used today in marine applications. The purpose of this article is to understand their interface phenomena and to compare flax/PLLA with others composites using microbond tests.

Keywords: Flax, Biopolymer, Biocomposite, interfacial properties, microbond test

INTRODUCTION

Biocomposites are being increasingly studied due to their good mechanical properties [1] biocompostability [2] and recyclability [3] and offer an interesting alternative to glass fibre/polyester composites. However so far few papers have described their interfacial properties while improvement of their performance and durability need a better understanding of this area. The aim of this work is to compare interfacial properties of Flax/Poly(L-Lactide) biocomposites with those of glass/polyester composites and others systems using a microbond test and contact angle measurement. Then cooling and annealing will be applied to understand the role of thermal stresses and polymer morphology on the interfacial properties. Finally analysis of friction and failure of microdroplet will be carried out.

1. Material and method

The biopolymer studied is a PLLA Poly(L-Lactic acid), the L9000 grade from Biomer®. The Resins are an isophthalic polyester (Norsodyne S 70361 TA with 1.5 wt% MEKP catalyst), and a DGEBA epoxy (AXSON Epolam 2015, with 32% by weight aliphatic amine hardener). Flax fibres, of the Hermès type, grown in Normandy were dew-retted before being stripped and combed. E-glass fibre from Chomar S.A. was used as comparison.

1.1 Microdroplet manufacturing

The first step is flax bundles separation in order to obtain single fibres. A fibre specimen is bonded to a thin paper which has a central longitudinal slot of fixed gage length. Each specimen is then examined under a microscope to check the fibre diameter.

Microdroplets are manufactured by tying a knot of PLLA around a single flax fibre. Then they are put in the oven. A suitable thermal treatment (Fig. 1) is needed to obtain a correct droplet (Fig.2.).

Fig. 1. Example of temperature programm for microdroplet manufacturing with cooling rate at 10 °C/min

Fig. 2. Example of correct PLLA microdroplet

Microbond specimens are finally checked under the microscope to control the droplet geometry, length and height. Samples with defects (kink band or lack of symmetry) are systematically removed. Besides being symmetrical, microdroplets need to be smaller than 250μm [4].

1.2 Microbond test

Micromechanical tests (fragmentation, pull-out, microbond, microindentation) have been developed as tools for the evaluation of adherence between the fibre surface and the matrix. These tests are described and their advantages and disadvantages discussed elsewhere [5]. One of the best-known is the microbond test, which consists of shearing a microdroplet of polymer off a single fibre (Fig. 3) [6, 7]. The microbond test has the advantage of a controlled embedded length, and makes it possible to study the wettability through contact angle measurement. However, the properties of flax fibres (scatter in mechanical characteristics, discontinuous fibres, and variable section) can influence the micro-tension test [8]. A tensile machine with a 2N sensor is used with tensile speed of 0.1 mm/min. During the test the force and the crosshead displacement are measured as shown in fig. 3 with a typical curve obtained (Fig. 4).

Fig.3 Schematic diagram of microbond test [6]

Fig.4 Force versus Crosshead displacement typical curve

Fig. 4 shows an example of a typical microbond test curve obtained for Flax/PLLA samples. Linear behaviour corresponding to elastic energy storage can be observed until

the force reaches the maximum force (F_{\max}). Once F_{\max} is reached the energy previously stored is released through fast interfacial cracking with a nearly constant friction force. Average Shear stress where a constant shear stress distribution is assumed along the interface can be estimated using equation 1 [9]:

$$\tau_{app} = \frac{F_{\max}}{2\pi r_f l_e} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where F_{\max} is the maximal force recorded, r_f is fibre radius and l_e the droplet length.

1.3 Contact angle measurement

The wetting behaviour of a fibre in liquid matrices plays an important role in the textile industry and in the fabrication of advanced fibre-reinforced composite materials. However even if a proper wetting is a necessary condition, it is not a sufficient condition to obtain a good composite assembly [10]. Natural fibre systems can show some differences compared to synthetic fibres [8]. The porous cell wall structure of plant fibres may induce important liquid penetration and a larger viscoelastic response to wetting compared to synthetic polymeric structures. Moreover complications may arise for vegetal fibre material since it is not only polymeric (as is the macromolecular cell wall component lignin, hemicellulose, and cellulose). Before debonding, the contact angles between the flax fibre and the solid matrix with the microdroplet are measured. Pictures of the droplet are transferred from Qwin software to Windrop⁺⁺ software, in order to determine contact angle. At the same time the ratio (Embedded length divided by the microdrop diameter) is determined.

1.4 Micromechanical analysis of the friction

Adherence mechanisms between fibres and matrix are complex. Unlike thermoset resins for which interfacial bonding is mainly formed by chemical bonds, adherence between fibres and thermoplastic resin result from physical interactions induced by compressive residual stresses [11-13]. In [14] interfacial residual stresses or interfacial pressure are evaluated by means of micromechanical models (Eq. 2).

$$\sigma_{rr}(r_f, z) = \frac{(1+\nu_f)(\alpha_m - \alpha_f)\Delta T}{\left(\frac{1-\nu_f}{E_f} + \frac{(1+\nu_m)}{E_m} - \frac{2\nu_f^2}{E_f} \right)} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where σ_{rr} is the radial stress, α is the thermal expansion coefficient (PLLA $\alpha_m = 78.5 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$ ($T < T_g$); Polyester $\alpha_m = 75 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$; Epoxy $\alpha_m = 70 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$; Flax $\alpha_f = -1 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$ and Glass $\alpha_f = 5 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$), ν is the Poisson's coefficient, E is the Young's modulus with f for fibre, m for matrix, l for longitudinal and t for transverse. ΔT is the difference between stress free temperature (crystallization temperature for semi-crystalline samples [15] and glass transition temperature for amorphous materials) and test temperature. This evaluates the temperature range where the thermal stress due to thermal shrinkage cannot be relaxed.

1.5 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

DSC tests were carried out with Mettler Toledo apparatus. The first scan of the thermogram was used because it includes the thermal history. Samples were heated to 190°C to determine crystallization and melting enthalpies. Crystallinity rate is estimated using equation 3.

$$\chi_c = \frac{\Delta H_m - \Delta H_c}{\Delta H_{0\%}} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

With ΔH_c and ΔH_m the crystallization and melting enthalpies. $\Delta H_{100\% \text{ crystalline}} = 93.7$ J/g [16] is the theoretical melting enthalpy of 100% crystalline PLLA. Then different cooling rates (corresponding to thermal treatment of microdroplet) have been applied to determine crystallization temperature T_c and glass transition temperature T_g .

1.6 Static tensile test

Dog-bone PLLA samples were manufactured by hot compression moulding in a normalized mould. Different cooling rates were achieved to correlate with microdroplet cooling kinetics and to determine the effect of cooling rate on the tensile and shear properties of the matrix. Tensile tests are carried out at 1mm/min following ISO 527 standard. A biaxial extensometer was used to determine Young modulus and Poisson's coefficient.

1.7 Polarization microscopy

PLLA is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic, during cooling crystallization phenomena occur. A specific matrix morphology, known as transcristallization, can appear around the fibre. To study interfacial morphology, a stack of polymer film/fibre/polymer film (sandwich) was prepared by hot compression [17] and observed with a microscope equipped with hot plates.

1.8 SEM examination

The fracture surfaces were analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The samples were sputter-coated with a thin layer of gold in an Edwards Sputter Coater, and analyzed with a Jeol JSM 6460LV scanning electron microscope.

2. Results

2.1 Microbond test

Using microbond tests, an average shear stress τ_{app} can be evaluated using Eq. 1. Moreover the effect of residual thermal stress can be determined through different thermal treatment (cooling rate and annealing under glass transition temperature) by means of an analysis of the microdroplet friction after debonding (Fig 4). The annealing treatment has been performed under T_g on quasi-amorphous samples (air cooled) in order to release residual stress without involving crystallization. Samples have been followed by DSC where endothermic peaks were observed around T_g (not shown here). The results are gathered in table 1.

Table 1. Influence of thermal treatments.

Material	Thermal treatment	τ_{app} (MPa)	$\tau_{friction}$ (MPa)	σ_{rr} (MPa)	Ref.
Flax/PLLA	Cooling	Air	15.3 ± 3.3	7.7 ± 1.5	5.52
		10°C/min	18.2 ± 1.8	8.2 ± 1.9	14.67
		1°C/min	22.2 ± 3.4	8.8 ± 3.3	18.3
	annealing	50°C during 72h	9.9 ± 1.5	6.4 ± 2.4	4.28
Flax/Epoxy	curing	65°C during 14h	16.1 ± 0.8	5.44 ± 2.18	5.74
Flax/Polyester			14.2 ± 0.4	9.81 ± 4.6	7.13
Glass/Epoxy			29.3 ± 2.4	7.7 ± 1.4	8.8
Glass/Polyester			14.2 ± 0.4	4.4 ± 0.7	10.6

First of all cooling rate has an important influence on interfacial properties of Flax/PLLA. Hence at low cooling rate the Average Shear Stress (IFSS) increases. Annealing of PLLA below T_g releases thermal stress and reduces interfacial properties of Flax fibre/PLLA (Table 1). Hence thermal residual stresses induced by rapid cooling rate have an influence on interfacial properties. The results also highlight that IFSS of Flax/PLLA systems are in the same range as those of Glass fibre/Polyester, Flax fibre/Polyester and Flax/Epoxy. It is important to note that glass fibres have specific sizings, which have been developed over many years.

Analysis of friction shows an increase of friction stress as well as radial stress σ_{rr} (or interfacial pressure) at low cooling rate, confirming the increasing role of residual stress. The interfacial pressure or radial stress originates from the matrix shrinkage and the resulting residual stress generated during cooling [6]. Release of thermal stress during annealing reduces friction stress and radial stress (Table 1). This follows the same trend as that observed for IFSS (Table 1.). Radial stresses in Flax/PLLA systems are higher than in Glass/Polyester and Flax/epoxy systems and are in the same range as glass/epoxy and Flax/Polyester. Indeed, the difference between expansion coefficients of flax fibre and PLLA are large compared to other systems. However, although the calculation of σ_{rr} takes into account the value of the thermal expansion coefficient of PLLA it is only determined over a small temperature range ($T < T_g$) which may underestimate the true value of α . Indeed determination of thermal expansion coefficients should involve all variation of free volume over the whole temperature range of microdroplet manufacturing.

Finally one has to keep in mind that the calculated interfacial pressure or radial stress is only an estimation. The scatter is important and the mechanisms involved are complex.

2.2 Study of contact angle and aspect ratio of microdroplets

Contact angles between flax fibres and PLLA matrix have been measured before debonding as well as their aspect ratio (embedded length/diameter). The results in Tab.2 show that the contact angle decreases with a low cooling rate (from $42.5^\circ \pm 9^\circ$ for air cooling to $33.5^\circ \pm 8.1^\circ$ at $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ cooling rate).

Moreover contact angle for PLLA droplets for each thermal treatment are larger (around double) compared to those of thermoset matrix with glass and flax fibre. These differences may not be explained by differences in surface tension (for PLLA $\gamma_s = 40.1 \pm 1.1 \text{ mJ}/\text{m}^2$ [18]; Polyester $\gamma_s = 44.2 \pm 1 \text{ mJ}/\text{m}^2$ [6] and for epoxy $\gamma_s = 40.8 \pm 2.3 \text{ mJ}/\text{m}^2$ [6]) but by the difference in shrinkage and by the magnitude of residual stress inside the

droplet. The aspect ratio (embedded length/diameter) shows good reproducibility between samples, and increases with low cooling rate which correlate with the trend followed by contact angles.

Table 2 Contact angle between flax fibres, glass fibres and resin (PLLA, Polyester and Epoxy) and aspect ratio of microdroplet (embedded length/diameter)

Material	Thermal treatment	θ (°)	L/d	Ref.
Flax/PLLA	Cooling	Air	42.5 ± 9	1.3 ± 0.1
		10°C/min	35.2 ± 10	1.34 ± 0.16
		1°C/min	33.5 ± 8.1	1.49 ± 0.9
	annealing	50°C during 72h	39.4 ± 10	1.34 ± 0.1
Flax/Epoxy	curing	65°C during 14h	17.3 ± 5.4	1.56 ± 0.09
Flax/Polyester			15.2 ± 2.3	1.65 ± 0.1
Glass/Epoxy			25.7 ± 2.1	1.52 ± 0.04
Glass/Polyester			15.5 ± 2.5	1.5 ± 0.14

[6]

2.3 Thermo-mechanical analysis of PLLA

Table 3 shows thermal properties of PLLA samples obtained with the same thermal treatment as the microdroplet. The values of crystallization and melting enthalpies have been taken from the first DSC scan to take into account the thermal history. The stress free temperature and ΔT are determined with suitable cooling rate monitored by the DSC device. Determination of ΔT values is important to evaluate thermal stresses induced by the cooling process [11]. When crystallization occurs during cooling, the stress free temperature is equal to crystallization temperature [15]. For slow and intermediate cooling, the crystallization temperature of PLLA is taken as the stress free temperature while for air cooled sample T_g is taken because no crystallization peak appears during cooling. ΔT values are higher with slow cooling rate.

Table 3. Thermal properties of PLLA

Material	thermal Treatment	Crystallization enthalpy (J/g)	Melting enthalpy (J/g)	Degree of crystallinity (%)	Stress free temperature T_{free} (°C)	ΔT ($T_{free} - T_{test}$)
PLLA	Air cooling	10.9	11.3	/	58	35
	10°C/min	7	18	11.7	102.4	79.4
	1°C/min	/	41	43	116.8	93.8
	annealing	9.4	10.5	0.01	58	35

Cooling rates modify as expected the crystalline structure of the PLLA matrix. The degree of crystallinity increases when cooling rate is slow (Table 3). Moreover ΔT values increase with decreasing cooling rate meaning that residual stresses increase with slow cooling kinetics. The annealing treatment under T_g does not induce crystallization mechanism.

Change of PLLA structure involves modification of mechanical properties such as tensile and shear properties (Table 4). As it is difficult to evaluate mechanical properties of microdroplets, tensile test samples were manufactured with controlled cooling rate.

For technical reasons it was not possible to reach exactly the same cooling rate (Table 4). Moreover air cooled droplets have a cooling rate which is not easy to quantify, but must be very quick given the small size of the specimen. We estimate for our tensile specimen that water cooling rate (93°C/min) is a correct approximation for air cooling of a microdroplet. Indeed thermal analyses (not shown here) have demonstrated similar trends with close values of crystallization and melting enthalpies to those of microdroplet samples.

Shear properties can be estimated through tensile properties by assuming an isotropic nature of the matrix (eq.4 et 5) :

$$G_m = \frac{E_m}{2(1+\nu_m)} \quad (\text{Eq.4.})$$

With G_m shear modulus of the matrix, E_m tensile modulus and ν_m poisson's coefficient

$$\tau_m = \frac{\sigma_m}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (\text{Eq.5.})$$

With τ_m the shear strength of the matrix, σ_m the tensile strength.

Thermal expansion coefficient was determined by DMA (compressive mode) over a temperature range from -20 to 60°C.

Table. 4. Tensile and shear properties of PLLA matrix as a function of thermal treatment

Material	Thermal treatment	E_m (MPa)	G_m (MPa)	σ_m (MPa)	τ_m (MPa)	ν_m	α (/°C) (T<Tg)
PLLA	93°C/min	3029 ± 410	1303 ± 476	56 ± 1	33 ± 0.6	0.162 ± 0.02	(78 ± 2.2) *10 ⁻⁶
	15.5°C/min	3743 ± 368	1609 ± 144	60.9 ± 3.2	35.2 ± 1.8	0.162 ± 0.03	
	1.5°C/min	4003 ± 410	1743 ± 176	64.4 ± 1	37.8 ± 3.3	0.148 ± 0.02	
	Annealing	3394 ± 149	1463 ± 120	58.3 ± 3	33.7 ± 1.7	0.163 ± 0.01	

Mechanical properties of the PLLA matrix change with cooling rate. With slow cooling rate (1.5°C/min), a high crystallinity rate of the PLLA improves tensile or shear properties. Increase of tensile modulus will influence the formation of residual stress [19]. Furthermore increase of Poisson's coefficient is noted when cooling rate is slow. Thermal expansion coefficient does not vary with cooling rate. Indeed this parameter has been determined only for a small temperature range below glass transition temperature (-20 to 60°C) for technical reasons. This range does not include a large variation of free volume compared to temperatures around the crystallization temperature [11]. Further analysis over a wider range would show variation of thermal expansion coefficient with degree of crystallinity.

2.4 Analysis of matrix and interfacial morphology

Polarization microscopy makes it possible to evaluate the polymer structure and to correlate the photos with DSC measurements. Figure 5a, 6a and 7a show results from PLLA/Flax/PLLA sandwich observations for different cooling rates, and a correlation with microdroplet samples.

Fig. 5 : Air cooling ; a : PLLA/flax/PLLA stack; b: microdroplet

Fig. 6 : 10°C/min ; a : PLLA/flax/PLLA stack; b : microdroplet

Fig. 7 : 1°C/min ; a : PLLA/flax/PLLA stack; b: microdroplet

Air cooled sample (Fig.5a) exhibits quasi-amorphous structure with very small and rare spherulites. Intermediate cooling of 10°C/min (Fig 6a) results in a few more spherulites with larger size. Then slow cooling rate samples (1°C/min) (Fig. 7a) have a crystalline structure with large spherulites. Some impurities or voids can be observed on these samples (arrow on Fig.7a). These observations correlate with DSC measurement.

In addition to matrix modification, cooling rate influences fibre/matrix interfacial area morphology as well. Besides a higher number of spherulites with slow cooling kinetics, one can notice a growing transcrystallization region around the flax fibre (Fig 6a and 7a). The formation mechanism and its effect on mechanical properties are still not clear and depend on the fibre/matrix studied [20].

2.5 SEM pictures

SEM pictures (Fig. 8a and b) show that PLLA droplets have different fracture mechanisms compared to epoxy droplets.

Interfacial bonding of Flax/PLLA exhibits adhesive fracture (Fig 8a) which confirm weak bond between fibre and polymer. For Epoxy droplet the crack is initiated in mode I in the matrix and propagates in the interfacial area (Fig 8b).

Fig. 8. a : PLLA microdroplet on flax fibre; b : Epoxy droplet cured at 65 °C

4. Discussion

Adherence mechanisms between fibres and matrix resins are complex. While interfaces with thermoset resins are governed by chemical bonds, adherence between fibres and thermoplastic resins appears to be governed by weak bonds such as Van der Waals interactions and mechanical anchoring induced by compressive residual stress [11-14].

Microbond tests allow the Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS) of Flax fibre/PLLA bonds to be estimated. Cooling kinetics have been shown to modify interfacial properties.

Indeed when cooling rate is slow, average Shear strength increases and a high degree of crystallinity is measured with transcrystallinity around the flax fibre (Fig 6a and 7a). The crystalline morphology of the matrix results in improvement of mechanical properties (tensile and shear) as well as reduction of Poisson's coefficient and higher residual compressive stress (Table 1). Furthermore the development of high crystallinity induces higher shrinkage of the matrix and thus increases the difference between thermal expansion coefficients of the matrix and the fibre. This difference generates residual compressive stresses which are involved in the stress transfer mechanism between matrix and fibre [11]. The magnitude of thermal residual stress is also influenced by ΔT ($T_{free} - T_{test}$). As cooling rate influences the temperature at which thermal stress are frozen [11] the slower the cooling rate the more T_{free} increases and as a consequence ΔT and thermal stress also increase. The difference in thermal coefficients and ΔT are taken into account in the micromechanical equation used to evaluate residual stress in Table 1.

Relaxation of residual stress due to annealing of quasi-amorphous specimens below glass transition temperature involves a decrease of interfacial properties. During rapid cooling the main structure is the amorphous phase and, depending on the visco-elastic behaviour of the matrix this may not have time to relax [11]. Thus the residual stresses that appear during this phase will control interfacial properties.

Besides matrix morphology the interfacial area is modified by the cooling rates. Indeed a transcrystallization phenomenon appears for slow cooling rates. The anisotropy of the transcrystalline zone increases both thermal stress [11, 21, 22] and mechanical anchorage between fibre and matrix [13]. The results from the present study are in agreement with those of [23, 24]. Fracture mechanisms (Fig 8a and 8b) are adhesive for Flax/PLLA bonds which confirm the weak interaction between flax fibres and PLLA.

The influence of thermal residual stress on interfacial mechanisms has also been evaluated by a micromechanical model. Friction stress and compressive stress increase with slow cooling rate, which is consistent with the trend of the interfacial properties.

In addition, contact angle measurements have highlighted the influence of cooling kinetics and polymer morphology on wetting angle (Table 2). Reduction of contact angle between flax and PLLA can influence average shear strength (Fig 7). Indeed Fig .7 shows that a relation may exist between the contact angle and the IFSS and thus adhesion and IFSS. Reduction of contact angle can reduce the stress concentration in the microdroplet specimen during microbond test.

Fig. 9 Evolution of Average Shear Strength as a function of Contact angle

Finally interfacial properties are controlled by two competitive mechanisms : Thermal residual stresses induced by crystallization and transcrystallization phenomena as well as ΔT (difference between stress free temperature and test temperature) for slow cooling rate and the matrix relaxation (linked to the visco-elastic behaviour of the matrix) for rapid cooling.

The use of a macromechanical approach (average shear Strength and Friction models) is however open to criticism. First, the average shear strength model is simple but this approach assumes a constant stress distribution along the interface while some authors [5, 25] have demonstrated that this is not the case. In addition this model does not take into account thermal stresses and produces scattered results which are hard to compare with other characterization methods.

An analysis of friction is necessary, and the model developed by [14], which includes thermal expansion coefficients and mechanical properties of the fibre, is useful. The way to determine α involves some errors because α characterization has only been possible for a temperature range below T_g (-20 to 60°C). The value obtained may not represent the true physical phenomenon since most of the decrease in free volume will occur around the crystallization temperature (for semi crystalline polymer). Finally, the use of natural fibres induces a lot of complexity in the analysis of the results because of the variability of their properties and geometry.

5. Conclusion

This paper presents results from a study on interfacial properties of a Flax fibre/PLLA system compared to other systems including Flax/Polyester, Flax/Epoxy, Glass fibre/Polyester and Glass/Epoxy.

Microbond test are used to estimate the interfacial shear strength. To have a better understanding of the phenomena which govern the interfacial mechanisms in Flax/PLLA biocomposite different thermal treatments (different cooling rate and annealing to release thermal stress) have been carried out resulting in different residual stress states inside the material. Interfacial properties of Flax/PLLA are in the same range as those measured on Glass/Polyester, and are influenced by the cooling kinetics. Results highlight that interfacial properties are controlled by two competitive mechanisms : Thermal residual stress induced by crystallization and transcristallization phenomena. Additional parameters are ΔT (the difference between stress free temperature and test temperature) for slow cooling rates, and the matrix relaxation governed by visco-elastic behaviour of the matrix at rapid cooling rate.

Furthermore contact angle measurements are also influenced by the cooling kinetics and polymer morphology (Table 2). Reduction of contact angle between flax and PLLA influences average shear strength by reducing the stress concentration in the microdroplet specimen during microbond tests.

Analysis of microdroplet friction after debonding was used to understand the influence of residual stresses. Slow cooling rate increase the friction stresses and the compressive stresses calculated by the model. Some limits to this approach have been highlighted. Further work is needed to measure surface tension of liquid PLLA, in order to correlate the work of adhesion and interfacial shear strength.

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